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THE HUMAN MIND AND ITS EMOTIONAL BALANCE

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ABSTRACT

Emotional intelligence (EI) is the ability to recognize, understand, and manage emotions, both your own and those of others. Having good emotional intelligence is essential for success in interpersonal relationships, as it allows for better communication and conflict resolution. EI involves skills such as: self-awareness, self-management, empathy, and social actions. Developing emotional intelligence can bring benefits: greater self-confidence, resilience, and better personal and professional relationships. Emotional management is related to the ability to regulate and maintain emotions, that is, to generate positive actions and reduce negative ones. People who are skilled at modifying emotions, adapting responses according to their goals and the environment, can obtain benefits in various situations and moments of stress, providing appropriate feedback to stressors. Having the ability to reduce intense emotions and calm down, when necessary, generating new emotional experiences, leading to feelings of self-control. More emotionally intelligent individuals have greater ease in dealing with disagreements, being more capable of facing changes. It is also important in the workplace, contributing to a good organizational climate and the development of effective leadership. Furthermore, IE can be learned and developed throughout life, through training, reading and daily practices. Investing in this process can bring significant benefits to mental health and human quality of life.

KEYWORDS: mind, interpersonal relationships, behaviors, emotional balance.